

A NOVEL TEXTILE PREFORMING AND JOINING TECHNIQUE BY THREAD-LESS NEEDLE STITCHING

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SUMMARY: A near net shaped textile preforming of fiber reinforcements is necessary for several the liquid closed molding process, which can manufacture the large scale of fiber-reinforced composite products with high cost-effectiveness and productivity. In this study, a novel textile preforming technique was realized by diverting the punch needle embroidery, which is a unique stitching method utilizing rarely in an apparel industry. Using this technique, the reinforcing fabrics can be joined by entangling some reinforcing fibers themselves without using any sewing threads. The main objective of this study is to verify the effectiveness on joining properties of nonwoven and woven cloth fabrics “needle-stitched” in various conditions. The effects of needle-stitching on interlaminar joining properties were showed by means of a single lap joint (SLJ) test and a double cantilever beam (DCB) test. The influences of damages on the fibers due to needle-stitching were also investigated by a tensile test. Continuous I-shaped structural member and complicated-shaped turbo-fan preforming were fabricated as the practical examples for showing the possibility of 3 dimensional near net shaped textile preforming.

KEYWORDS: Textile preforming, Needle stitching, Near net shape, Interlaminar shear strength, Interlaminar fracture toughness

INTRODUCTION

Recently the liquid closed molding processes, such as various resin transfer molding (RTM) and vacuum assisted resin infusion (VARI) processes are paid an attention for cost reduction and environmental-friendly processing in manufacture of fiber reinforced polymer composites in comparison with an autoclaving and hand-lay up methods, respectively. In those productions, the near net shape textile preforming can be a key technology for cost-effective and high quality controlled productions in addition to the improvements of resin flow behaviors, such as lower viscosity of matrix resin, surface treatment of fibers and prediction by numerical simulation. So far, the conventional stitching, i.e. sewing, technique has been developed and applied for a wet manufacturing processes of large-scale advanced composite structures such as airplane and aerospace applications. In such a preforming, sewing threads interlocks with chain stitching between the reinforcing layers, and then the interlaminar shear strength can be remarkably increased. On the contrary to this benefit, the sewing thread is generally too strong, and the preforming is too rigid to be deformed flexibly the fiber reinforcements during the setting-up on the die. Furthermore, the sewing threads become risky to introduce the interfacial debonding and crack from their surface especially in cyclic or creep loading under acid corrosive environmental conditions, because the interfacial strength between the sewing threads and its surrounding matrix is generally weaker than the strength between the reinforcing fiber and matrix. Therefore the research and development of the novel preforming technique without using sewing threads would be demanded.

PREFORMING TECHNIQUES

Several conventional textile preforming techniques, which are utilizing for liquid moldings in the current composites manufactures, are summarized in Table I. The requirements for textile preforming are listed as below; 1) Potential of complicated near-net shape, 2) Less barrier to resin impregnation, 3) Durability and reliability for damages and 4) High productivity with low cost. Attempts are being made to reduce the cost by automating the production of preform such as Ford's programmable preform processing system [1] and the advanced sewing system developed ALTIN Naatechnik GmbH [2].

Table I Comparison of several conventional preforming techniques

Methods	Advantages	Disadvantages
Pressing	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ Not using distinct kind of materials ✓ High workability ✓ Potential to deep-drape 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ Need for large equipment and dies ✓ Inhomogeneous fiber fraction ✓ <u>Limited form, i.e. only shell shape</u>
Adhesive bonding	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ High workability ✓ Low stress concentrations ✓ Low cost 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ <u>Using distinct kind of materials with low thermal and physical properties</u> ✓ <u>Barrier to resin impregnation</u>
Sewing	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ Various complicated form, e.g. box-shape closed structures ✓ High interlaminar joining strength ✓ Using conventional sewing machine 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ <u>Using distinct kind of materials with poor interfacial properties</u> ✓ Tight restraint, the resultant disorder to fiber placements

NEEDLE STITCHING METHOD

A needle punching method has been using for continuous production of non-woven fabrics, carpets and blankets with hairy fabric, since around 1960's. In this process, web consolidation or non-woven joining processes interlock preferentially arranged fiber assemblies by mechanical mean. On the other hand, punch needle embroidery is the art of working one basic stitch with a hollow needle to create a raised ornamental design on woven fabric. Punch embroidery requires no knotting. It is durable and machine washable. Various types of threads can be used on different fabrics.

We tried to develop a novel type of textile preforming and joining method using the punch needle embroidery technique, which is likely to familiar as traditional craft works in Unites States. This technique is not necessary to use any threads but entangled reinforcing yarns each other with multiple needles as shown in Fig.1a. The needle has triangular sections, is the special needle, which possesses two grooves in each side. As shown in Fig.1b, the upper reinforcing yarns are carried to lower reinforcing layer by triangle needle with grooves, and caught with lower reinforcing yarns. In such a way, the joining of layers results from moving the upper reinforcing yarns to lower layer. Then number of interlaminar binding yarns is dependent on the needle penetrations as function of needle arrangements and fabric feeding speed, but the degree of surface treatment of yarns might be a primary factor in determining the interlaminar joining strength. The advantages of this method are listed as follow; 1) The distinct materials other than the reinforcing fibers are not used, 2) The permeation of the resin is not obstructed compared with adhesive bonding, and 3) The degree of freedom for deformation is high. However some disadvantages are expected as follow; 1) Severe damages are given to the reinforcing fibers during stitching process, and 2) Joining strength is weak in comparison with conventional stitching method.

Fig.2 Effect of stitching angle on arrangement of needle hole.

EXPERIMENTAL DETAILS

Preparations of test specimens and stitching conditions

The reinforcements used in this study are E-glass fiber chopped strand mat and woven cloth fabrics as listed in Table II. The dry fabrics joined by needle-stitching were evaluated on the tensile and interlaminar joining properties for several test specimens as illustrated in Fig.3. The composite specimens were also examined using those fabrics for the comparisons. The specimens were prepared using vinyl-ester resin and hardeners shown in Table II by hand-lay up method for convenience.

The fabrics cut in desired shapes are needle-stitched at approximate constant feed speed of fabrics under the sewing conditions as listed in Table III, where repeat count of stitching means iteration times for stitching operations, stitching line means the number of stitching in different positions. The arrangement of needle hole is dependent on the stitching angle as shown in Fig.2. The in-plane density of stitching is basically inverse-proportional to the feed speed of fabrics, but is not simply decided because of the multiple needles. The arrangements of needle are necessary to be optimized for higher efficiency of stitching effect. In this study, the commercial needle embroidery sewing machine as listed in Table III was used in the laboratory.

Table II Specifications for materials used in the experiments

	Type of reinforcement	Products ID	Thickness
E-glass fiber	Non-woven strand mat	MCE450-104SS (Nittobo Co., Ltd.)	1mm
	Plain woven fabric	YEM-2103-N7 (Mie-Fabrics Co., Ltd.)	0.2mm
	Chemical composition	Products ID	Ratio in mass
Resin	Vinyl-ester resin	R806B (Showa Highpolymer Co., Ltd.)	100
Curing remoter	$[C_{18}H_{30}O_2]_2Co$ (5wt% in Mineral spirit agent)	Generic chemical agents	0.3
Catalyst	Methyl Ethyl Ketone Peroxide, MEKPO (6wt% in DOP agent)	Generic chemical agents	1

Table III Sewing machine and stitching conditions used in the experiments

Type of machine	Products ID	Number of needle	Needle distance
Needle embroidery sewing machine	NPI-36S (Tanaka & Co., Ltd.)	36	3mm (Min) 6mm (Max)
Repeat count of stitching, nr (times)	Number of stitching line, nl (lines)	Stitching angle, θ (deg.)	Number of ply, np (plies)
(0), 1, 2, 3, 4, 5	(0), 1, 2, 3, 5	90	1, 3, 5

Tensile and Interlaminar shear strengths

The influences of damages in fiber reinforcements resulting from needle-stitching were investigated by tensile test for both dry fabrics and composite specimens (Fig.3a). Using the maximum tensile load, P_{max} obtained from experimental results, the tensile strength, σ of laminas was given by $\sigma = P_{max} / (w \cdot t)$. On the other hand, the effects of needle-stitching on joining properties were

evaluated by the single lap-joint (SLJ) test (Fig.3b), the interlaminar shear strength, τ was given by $\tau = P_{\max}/(w \square l)$.

Interlaminar fracture toughness

The interlaminar fracture toughness is evaluated by mode I energy release ratio, G_I of DCB specimen (Fig.3c), which is given by Eqn.1:

$$G_I = \frac{P^2}{2w} \cdot \frac{dC}{da} \text{----- (1)}$$

where load-line compliance, C and crack length, a are obtained experimentally. The compliance, C is defined as the ratio of the load point displacement, δ to applied load, P , and then expressed by the elastic beam theory as Eqn.2:

$$C = \frac{\delta}{P} = \frac{2a^3}{3E_f I} = \frac{8a^3}{E_f w h^3} \text{----- (2)}$$

where E_f and I ($=wh^3/12$) are longitudinal flexural modulus and geometrical moment inertia, respectively. The relationship between compliance, C and crack length, a is given approximately by Eqn.3:

$$\frac{a}{H} = A_0 + A_1 C^{1/3} \text{----- (3)}$$

Then, the coefficients, A_0, A_1 were obtained by experimental results, finally mode I energy release ratio, G_I can be expressed as Eqn.4, which is not related to crack length, a :

$$G_I = \frac{3P^2 C^{2/3}}{2wA_1 h} \text{----- (4)}$$

EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

Tensile strength

Fig.4 shows the tensile strength of dry fabrics needle-stitched with various repeat count of stitching. With both random mat and woven cloth fabrics, the tensile strength significantly decreases as the repeat count of stitching increases. Woven cloth fabric is much larger in the reduction ratio of tensile strength than random mat fabric. This is due to the microscopic damages, which are given on the surface of fibers by needle-stitching operations. In turn, Fig.5 shows the tensile strength of composites reinforced by these fabrics, which were needle-stitched with various repeat count of stitching. The percentage in tensile strength reduction against as-received fabric ($nr=0$) reinforced specimens reaches 20% in case of repeat count of stitching, $nr=5$. However in case of woven cloth composites as shown in Fig.5b, there is no significant difference in tensile strength between non-stitched ($nr=0$) and $nr=3$ specimens. Therefore the needle-stitching operation significantly affects the tensile strength of dry fabrics, but this is valid in composite manufactures if acceptable. The excess degree of needle-stitching should be avoided at any rate, and the appropriate surface treatment of fiber may be efficient for preventing a big damage occurrence.

(a) Glass random mat fabric

(b) Glass woven cloth fabric

Fig.4 Tensile strength as function of repeat count of stitching (in case of dry fabrics).

(a) Glass random mat composite

(b) Glass woven cloth composite

Fig.5 Tensile strength as function of repeat count of stitching (in case of composites).

Interlaminar shear strength

Fig.6 shows the interlaminar shear strength of dry fabrics needle-stitched with various repeat count of stitching. With random mat fabric (Fig.6a), the interlaminar shear strength significantly increases as the repeat count of stitching increases, and the fracture switched from the interlaminar shearing mode to the tensile mode at repeat count of stitching more than $nr=2$. This means that the joining strength between random mat fabrics grows extremely by needle-stitching operation of iteration twice at least. With woven cloth fabrics (Fig.6b), the interlaminar shear strength grows exponentially. It is therefore obvious that the needle-stitching operations can provide the dry fabrics a higher interlaminar joining strength. Fig.7 shows the interlaminar shear strength of composites reinforced by fabrics, which were needle-stitched with various repeat count of stitching. In the SLJ test of random mat composites (Fig.7a), the interlaminar shearing fracture did not occur in any specimens, thus the interlaminar shear strength is much higher than the tensile strength. With woven cloth composites (Fig.7b), the interlaminar shear strength linearly increases with an increasing of the repeat count of stitching. It is realized from these results that the needle-stitching operation make an enhanced interlaminar joining.

(a) Glass random mat fabric

(b) Glass woven cloth fabric

Fig.6 Interlaminar shear strength as function of repeat count of stitching (in case of dry fabrics).

(a) Glass random mat composite

(b) Glass woven cloth composite

Fig.7 Interlaminar shear strength as function of repeat count of stitching (in case of composites).

Interlaminar fracture toughness

Fig.8 shows the applied load - load point displacement curves obtained in DCB tests for random mat and woven cloth composites. The maximum loads of random mat composite are higher than that of woven cloth ones. As the repeat count of stitching increases, the maximum load at which initiated an interlaminar delamination, increases remarkably in both DCB composite specimens. In case of stitched woven cloth composite specimens ($nr=1, 3, 5$), the interlaminar delamination propagated to the non-stitched interlaminar plane after reaching the maximum load, because the needle-stitched interlaminar plane is very high for a tearing resistance. In case of woven cloth composite specimens, on the other hand, the interlaminar delamination is the dominant fracture mode. With non-stitched specimen ($nr=0$), the unstable fracture mode is a most visible behavior among them. It is thought that this is the reason because the crack propagated on the surface of woven cloth. From these results, it is obvious that the needle-stitching is an effective operation for providing the resistant to a tearing force.

Fig.9 mode-I energy release rate, G_{IR} (J/mm²) versus repeat count of stitching, nr (times). The graph shows that the Mode I energy release rate, G_{IR} , increases with the repeat count of stitching, nr , for both glass random mat composite (a) and glass woven cloth composite (b). This indicates that the needle-stitching operation has a great potential to avoid propagating the interlaminar delamination in practical.

(a) Glass random mat composite

(b) Glass woven cloth composite

Fig.9 Effect of repeat count of stitching on interlaminar fracture toughness.

EXAMPLES OF NEAR NET SHAPED TEXTILE PREFORMING

I-shaped structural member

In order to show the possibility of 3 dimensional textile preforming using the needle-stitching, the continuous I-shaped structural member was fabricated as shown in Fig.10. In case of such a simple shape, the endless preformed products are basically capable to make using any fibers. The easiness to decompose, i.e. “undo” and rebuild this preformed product (if needed) is also a feature in this method.

(a) Fabric placement and stitching positions

(b) Preformed product

Fig.10 An example of textile preforming: Continuous I-shaped structure member.

Turbo fan

Fig.11 shows an example of textile preforming for turbo fan with complicated shape impeller. It is verified that the needle-stitching techniques can not be applied for only several simple shapes, such as shell, tube, box, etc, but also flexibly for many assembled structures with 3 dimensional curvatures.

(a) Composite product (impeller) (b) Preformed product (impeller and base-plate)

(c) Preformed product (Overall of turbo fan)

Fig.11 An example of textile preforming: Turbo fan.

CONCLUSIONS

This study showed the effectiveness of the implementation of needle-stitching technique for near net shaped textile preforming and joining properties of non-weaving and woven cloth fabrics.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

The authors express appreciation for the cooperation by Mr. Osamu Tanaka, President of Tanaka & Co., Ltd., and Mr. Kenji Kabuto, a former student of Osaka Prefectural College of

Technology.

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